

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Process Safety and Environmental Protection

journal homepage: www.journals.elsevier.com/process-safety-and-environmental-protection

Avoiding runaway scenarios in Fischer-Tropsch synthesis during startup: temperature and pressure influence

Karen Quintana^{a,b}, Martí Biset-Peiró^a, Andrés A. García Blanco^a , Jordi Guilera^{a,b,*}

^a Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de les Dones de Negre 1, Adrià, Besòs, 08930, Spain

^b Facultat de Química, Universitat de Barcelona, Martí i Franquès, 1, Adrià, Besòs, Barcelona 08028, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Reactor startup
Runaway prevention
Catalytic reaction control

ABSTRACT

The operation of Fischer-Tropsch synthesis (FTS) pilot plants is essential to advancing Power-to-X strategies. However, conducting experimental campaigns with multiple startups introduces significant challenges due to the system's pronounced sensitivity to thermal instability and remains an unaddressed challenge in the literature. This experimental study analyzes the thermal response of a pilot-scale FTS reactor under controlled heating and pressurization, aiming to identify safe operating limits to prevent thermal runaway. In this experimental work, runaway was observed when the heating rate response (HRR) exceeded 15 °C/h, while stable operation was achieved by limiting oil heating to <1 °C/h. Pressurization from 10 to 20 bar at 3 bar/h induced a significantly lower thermal rate of 0.48 °C/bar, offering an alternative to thermal ramping below 210 °C. These findings highlight the importance of combining temperature and pressure ramping strategies to maintain thermal control during startup and underscore the need to evaluate the heating rate response continuously and maintain it below the critical threshold to ensure safe and stable operation.

1. Introduction

Fischer-Tropsch synthesis (FTS) is a key reaction in the utilization of non-petroleum carbon resources for the sustainable production of clean liquid fuels from synthesis gas (Zhang et al., 2014). Since its discovery in 1923, the FTS process has been acknowledged as a highly promising technology for transforming carbon monoxide and hydrogen, derived from abundant coal and natural gas reserves, into synthetic liquid fuels and valuable chemical products (Fratolocchi et al., 2020). The increasing demand for alternative energy sources has revitalized interest in the FTS process, as it offers a direct and environmentally sustainable method for producing high-quality synthetic fuels and feedstock chemicals, such as kerosene or maritime gasoil (Hamer et al., 2023; Quintana et al., 2024).

The highly exothermic nature of the FTS process ($\Delta H_R^0 \approx -165 \text{ kJ/mol}_{\text{CO}}$), coupled with its significant sensitivity to temperature variations, presents challenges in thermal heat management, in fixed-bed reactors, even using narrow diameter tubes (<50 mm) (Fratolocchi et al., 2020). Effective temperature control is essential to prevent excessive heat rises, which can lead to suboptimal product distribution, catalyst degradation, and potential thermal runaway. In

this aspect, thermal runaway is a critical hazard in industrial processes involving exothermic reactions, characterized by an uncontrolled acceleration of reaction rates that leads to rapid increases in temperature and pressure. If not properly managed, it can result in severe consequences, including equipment failure, explosions, and serious safety risks (Kummer and Varga, 2021; Saada et al., 2015). Preventing thermal runaway requires a combination of technical strategies—such as optimized reactor design and efficient cooling systems—and organizational measures like comprehensive operator training and rigorous safety protocols (Zhang et al., 2021).

While many studies focus on optimizing FTS operation (Chikati et al., 2024; Fernandes, 2006; Kaskes et al., 2016; Pandey et al., 2022), the development of reliable startup protocols remains a critical yet scarcely documented aspect in scientific literature. Several patents detail FTS startup procedures, emphasizing the economic risks associated with poor temperature regulation during this phase (Arcuri and Rouge, 1986). Recent patents highlight the profound influence of startup strategies on process efficiency, productivity, and catalyst activity. For instance, BP and Johnson Matthey's procedure involves precise temperature control, starting at 150 °C with a gradual increase of 2 °C/h to 205 °C, and holding for 200 h before rising to 212 °C for an additional

* Corresponding author at: Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de les Dones de Negre 1, Adrià, Besòs, 08930, Spain.

E-mail address: jguilera@irec.cat (J. Guilera).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2025.107849>

Received 1 July 2025; Received in revised form 28 August 2025; Accepted 6 September 2025

Available online 9 September 2025

0957-5820/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of Institution of Chemical Engineers. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

280 h—a startup process exceeding 400 h (Hamer et al., 2023). Shell's approach incorporates a nitrogen-containing compound, such as ammonia, in the feed gas to mitigate catalyst deactivation caused by high relative humidity during startup. While this strategy temporarily reduces C₅₊ selectivity, it enhances long-term stability, delaying deactivation and extending operational lifespan (Bezemer et al., 2025). These extended startup protocols, while effective for industrial-scale operations, are not feasible in R&D pilot-scale settings, where multiple startups are required throughout an experimental campaign (Boymans et al., 2025; Ermolaev et al., 2015; Shen et al., 2020; Visconti et al., 2024).

Pilot-scale studies report unstable conditions, thermal runaway (Boymans et al., 2025), or only isolated data points (Ermolaev et al., 2015; Shen et al., 2020), highlighting the lack of standardized startup and operational methodologies. To address these challenges, recent research has focused on developing structured internals for fixed-bed reactors, aimed at improving heat management and preventing thermal runaway. For example, Boymans et al. evaluated four different internal configurations using a FTS startup procedure based on a controlled heating rate of 2 °C/h applied to the thermal oil and reactor wall. However, despite this protocol, thermal runaway occurred in three configurations before reaching the target temperature. Only the system equipped with a 3D-printed copper internal achieved stable operation, significantly improving heat transfer by conduction and thereby enhancing thermal stability and productivity (Boymans et al., 2025). Besides, long-term pilot-scale operations are relatively scarce (Gholami et al., 2023; Ghouri et al., 2016). Notably, Fratolocchi et al. and Visconti et al. reported stable performance over 600 h—Fratolocchi et al. using packed POCs in an automated lab-scale setup (Fratolocchi et al., 2020), and (Visconti et al., 2024) employing tubular reactors equipped with cellular internals and isothermal oil cooling. Both systems operated within the temperature and pressure ranges of 180–230 °C and 15–25 bar.

In this context, the present study aims to analyze the thermal behavior inside the reaction bed during controlled heating and pressurization at the startup of a fixed-bed FTS pilot reactor loaded with a micro-sized catalyst, with the objective of establishing its thermal rate boundaries. The goal is to support the development of controlled startup procedures that minimize the risk of thermal runaway. By providing insights into safe and reproducible operating conditions, this work contributes to the standardization of startup protocols in applied FTS research, thereby promoting scalability and facilitating the transfer of laboratory-scale advances to industrial applications.

2. Methodology

2.1. Reaction Kinetics of FTS

The primary reaction of FTS, leading predominantly to paraffinic C₂₊ hydrocarbons, is as follows (Visconti et al., 2024):

The complex reaction mechanisms and numerous chemical species involved in the FT reaction make it challenging to describe its kinetics. Due to the low activity of the water gas shift (WGS) reaction, the rate expressions for Co-based FT catalysts have traditionally only included the partial pressures of H₂ and CO. Therefore, the irreversible power-law kinetics shown in Eq. (2) can be used to estimate the CO consumption (Dai et al., 2014):

$$r_{\text{CO}} = A e^{-E_a/RT} \cdot P_{\text{H}_2}^m \cdot P_{\text{CO}}^n \quad (2)$$

The kinetic parameters A , E_a , m and n were adopted from Dai et al. (2014): $A = 2.45 \times 10^6 \text{ mol}/(\text{kg} - \frac{\text{cat}}{\text{MPa}^{0.33}})$, $E_a = 73 \text{ kJ/mol}$, $m = 1.3$, $n = -1$.

2.2. Pilot-plant configuration

The pilot plant used in this study was developed as part of the SUPORT project (Development of a sustainable route to produce synthetic green fuels for maritime transport). The goal of the R&D initiative is to develop a cost-competitive, sustainable pathway for producing synthetic marine fuels (e-MGO) through an integrated process combining co-electrolysis of water and CO₂ with FTS (IREC, 2023). This plant is composed of four main sections: (i) gas feed, (ii) reaction, (iii) product separation, and (iv) online gas product analysis, as is shown in Fig. 1. The gas feed section consists of three independent lines supplying H₂ (5.0, Linde), carbon monoxide (4.7, Linde), and nitrogen (5.0, Linde), the latter used as an internal standard. Each line is equipped with a filter and a mass flow controller (MFC, F-201CV-10K-RAD-22-V, Bronkhorst) to ensure precise flow regulation. The feed gases are mixed and subsequently passed through a preheating system, which consists of a thermal oil bath (MAGIO MS-BC4, Julabo) to raise the temperature before entering the reactor.

The reactor used in this study is a tubular fixed-bed reactor with an internal diameter of 21.2 mm and a total length of 450 mm. It is externally heated and cooled using a thermal oil (Julabo Thermal HS) circulated in counter-current to the gas flow. The reactor was specifically designed to enable temperature monitoring along the entire bed length, with a spatial resolution of 32 mm, by means of a multipoint thermocouple probe (Omega), provided with 6 temperature measuring points (MP), located in the center of the catalyst bed (Fig. 1). Two representative examples of continuous monitoring, corresponding to the experiments shown in Figs. 4–6, are presented in Figures S1 and S2. The first temperature MP reported (1) is located at 11.1 cm from the reactor inlet. Experiments were conducted using 50 g a micro-size catalyst containing ~15.0 wt% cobalt supported on a commercial alumina support ($\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $d_p = 400\text{--}500 \mu\text{m}$ micro-spheres, Norpro Saint-Gobain), synthesized via the conventional wet impregnation method (Guilera et al., 2019). Characterization of the unreduced catalyst and its proper pre-treatment conditioning is detailed in a previous study (Lwazzani et al., 2024).

The reaction products exit the reactor and enter a first-phase separator maintained at 170 °C by means of an external heating jacket (HORST). In this unit, heavy hydrocarbons (waxes) are condensed and separated from the vapor phase, which contains middle distillates, light hydrocarbons, water, and unconverted reactants (CO and H₂). The vapor stream is then cooled using a thermal bath with cooling water at 6 °C and directed to a cold trap. Within the cold trap, water and middle distillates are separated from the remaining tail gas, which primarily consists of unconverted reactants and light hydrocarbons (C₁–C₄). Finally, non-condensable gases are sent to a back-pressure regulator, analyzed and finally vented to the atmosphere.

2.3. Experimental procedures

The experimental campaign was conducted under FTS process conditions representative of industrial operation: oil temperatures ranging from 190 to 202 °C, pressure of 10–20 bar, syngas with a H₂/CO feed ratio of 2:1 mol/mol, and a gas hourly space velocity (GHSV) of 1250 cm³/h.g_{cat}. 5 mol% of N₂ was added in the feed gas as internal standard for proper quantification of CO conversion. The influence of different heating rates in the reactor during startup was evaluated at 10 bar and 20 bar, as well as the influence of reactor pressurization on reactor temperature. In addition, the impact of varying the GHSV on the thermal response was analyzed in the range of 500–2000 cm³/h.g_{cat}.

Before catalytic tests, the catalyst was pre-reduced ex-situ in a furnace, under H₂ (10 vol%) at 420 °C for 16 h (heating rate of 1 °C/min). The reactor was then loaded with 50 g of the reduced catalyst and with alumina particles (1 mm diameter) above and below the catalyst bed (outside of the reaction zone), as shown in Fig. 2. Initially, leak tests were performed to ensure safety and verify system integrity, with

Fig. 1. Schematic of pilot plant configuration.

Fig. 2. FTS reactor and catalyst loading arrangement, with 6 temperature measuring points.

acceptance criteria defined as a depressurization rate below 0.4 bar/h. This aligns with the engineering rule of thumb that permits a pressure drop of less than 1 % of the test pressure over a period of 60 min (Okano et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2022). After confirming leak-tightness, the

catalyst was pre-treated in-situ by introducing H_2 at a flow rate of $100 \text{ Ncm}^3/\text{min}$ and kept at $240 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 10 bar during 24 h. Subsequently, the reactor was cooled down to $160 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to initiate operation. During this heating period, blanks were collected to establish baseline measurements for CO conversion calculation. Afterwards, syngas was introduced and heated to $190 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at a rate of $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{h}$. Subsequently, the oil bath was initially heated from $190 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $198 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at a rate of $8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{h}$ ($2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ increments every 15 min). Beyond $198 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the heating rate was reduced to increments of, at maximum, $0.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ every 15 min ($0.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{h}$).

2.4. Monitoring

Gaseous products were analyzed using an online micro Gas Chromatograph (Agilent 490) equipped with a dual-channel system. The first channel employed a 10 m MS5A PLOT column (molecular sieve 5 \AA) with Ar as the carrier gas to measure H_2 , N_2 , CO, and CH_4 . The second channel used a 10 m Poraplot-U column with He as carrier gas to detect CO_2 , C_2H_6 , and C_2H_4 .

CO conversion (X_{CO}) was calculated according to Eq. (3):

$$X_{CO}(\%) = \frac{F_{CO,in} - F_{CO,t}}{F_{CO,in}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where $F_{CO,in}$ is the molar flow rate of CO before reaction (blank measurements), and $F_{CO,t}$ is the molar flow rate at the outlet under reaction conditions at time t . $F_{CO,t}$ was determined relative to the internal standard (N_2) in the effluent stream.

Liquid and wax fractions were analyzed using a Gas Chromatograph/Mass Selective Detector (GC/MSD) system (Agilent 5975 C TAD) to identify and quantify the composition of the condensed products.

Selectivity to a specific hydrocarbon product i (S_i) was calculated according to Eq. (4):

$$S_i(\%) = \frac{n_i \cdot F_{i,t}}{F_{CO,0} - F_{CO}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where n_i corresponds to the number of carbon atoms of product i , and F_i is the molar flow rate of the species i at reaction time t .

During the startup period, the thermal response inside the reactor was monitored. This parameter, referred to as the heating rate response (HRR), was calculated as:

$$HRR(\text{°C}/\text{h}) = \frac{\Delta T_z}{\Delta t} = \frac{T_{i+1} - T_i}{t_{i+1} - t_i} \quad (5)$$

where T_i and T_{i+1} are consecutive temperature measurements, and t_i and t_{i+1} are the corresponding time values. The time interval (Δt) was defined according to the interval of which oil temperature was changed, typically ranging from 15 to 30 min.

To analyze the system behavior during startup in quantitative terms, the volumetric heat duty (Q_{vol}) – a key parameter associated with FT synthesis and heat transfer in the system – was calculated according to Eq. (6). This parameter represents the estimated heat released by the reaction, normalized to the volume of the catalyst bed (V_{cat}) (Panzeri et al., 2025).

$$Q_{vol} (\text{kW}/\text{m}^3_{cat}) = \frac{F_{CO}^{in} \cdot X_{CO} \cdot \Delta H_R^0}{V_{cat}} \quad (6)$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of heating ramps

Fig. 3(a) presents the temperature profiles recorded for the test of a fresh catalyst at the different temperatures MP within the reactor and at the thermal oil system during the startup heating phase at 10 bar. As described in Section 2.4, the system was initially heated externally at a controlled rate of 8 °C/h during the first hour, which was subsequently reduced to 0.8 °C/h. Below 192 °C (within the first 0.25 h), the system exhibited predominantly isothermal behavior, with close agreement between the oil bath temperature and the temperatures measured within the catalyst bed. Only a slight deviation (~3 °C) toward lower temperatures is observed at MP 1, which is attributed to feed gases entering the reactor below 180 °C (measured at 7.9 cm from the gas inlet), and to potential heat losses from the contact between the oil and the reactor walls along the catalyst bed.

As seen, above ~194 °C (0.5 h) the temperatures start to diverge due to the chemical reaction, indicating spatial differences in heat transfer dynamics. The temperature at the end of the catalyst bed (MP 6) exhibited the most significant increase, peaking at 225 °C. Fig. 3(b) presents the HRR at the different MPs. Notably, MP 6 displayed the highest HRR, accelerating sharply from 6 °C/h to 35 °C/h in 0.75 h. This steep increase in the thermal rate correlates with the beginning of a

thermal runaway event and indicates the location of hot spot formation. The observed temperature rate trend closely resembles the behavior reported by Boymans et al. (2025) for packed-bed systems, where they observed a HRR of 6.7 °C/h between 210–220 °C and 15 °C/h between 220–230 °C.

Fig. 4 shows the reactor's thermal rate using the same start-up heating conditions of the previous experiment, but with a catalyst that was previously kept under reaction for more than 40 h. In Fig. 4(a), the temperature evolution at reactor MP 1–6 is shown as the oil temperature increases from 190 °C to 198.6 °C. The temperature rise along the catalyst bed during the first 0.5 h was similar to that observed for the catalyst immediately after H₂ treatment showed in Fig. 3. At approximately 194°, the onset of the chemical reaction results in a noticeable increase in temperature, as observed in repeated startups, with the reactor temperature becoming higher than the oil bath. Nevertheless, the gradual and controlled temperature rise along the catalyst bed suggests that, under these conditions, the reactor remained stable and avoided thermal runaway.

As shown in Fig. 4(b), the HRR under these conditions remained below 15 °C/h throughout the process. It also indicates that the rising trend shown at MP 4, 5, and 6 changed when the heating rate of the oil bath decreased from 8 °C/h to 0.8 °C/h (after 1 h). This behavior contrasts with the thermal runaway observed in Fig. 3(b), where significantly higher heating rates were recorded. The difference between the two experiments is attributed to a decrease in the catalyst's activity due to prior use. However, the key finding of this experiment is that startup heating can be effectively controlled when the HRR is kept below 15 °C/h. This finding is particularly relevant given the potential variations in activity among different catalysts tested under pilot plant conditions, and it underscores the importance of calculating the HRR inside the reactor to ensure proper startup control. In this experiment, at a maximum temperature (T_{max}) of 205 °C, the CO conversion (X_{CO}) was 16.8 % and the heat release (Q_{vol}) reached 89.8 kW/m³.

Building on these insights, Fig. 5 shows the temperature profile of the reactor and the oil system during a controlled heating experiment at 10 bar and temperatures of the external oil bath higher than 198 °C. In Fig. 5(a), the reactor temperature is compared to the oil temperature while it gradually increased from 198.8 °C to 201 °C. At these temperatures, the difference between the reactor's temperature and the recirculating oil increases, as well as the temperature differences along the catalyst bed due to the increased activity of the reaction. Also, because of these more active reaction conditions, the thermal response of the catalyst bed to the oil bath ramp is more pronounced. The increase in oil bath temperature led to a change in the reactor temperature at MP 3

Fig. 3. Effect of oil heating on reactor temperature at 10 bar. (a) Temperature profile at reactor points T1 to T6. (b) Corresponding reactor thermal rate in the FTS reactor. Reaction conditions: P = 10 bar; GHSV = 1250 Ncm³.h⁻¹.g_{cat}⁻¹.

Fig. 4. Effect of oil heating on reactor temperature at 10 bar, during reactor heating from 190 °C to 205 °C. (a) Temperature profile at reactor points 1–6. (b) Corresponding reactor thermal rate in the FTS reactor. Reaction conditions: $P = 10$ bar; $GHSV = 1250 \text{ Ncm}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$.

Fig. 5. Effect of thermal oil heating on reactor temperature during startup from 200 °C to 217 °C at 10 bar. (a) Temperature profile recorded at reactor thermocouples T1–T6. (b) Corresponding reactor thermal rate in the FTS reactor. Reaction conditions: $P = 10$ bar; $GHSV = 1250 \text{ Ncm}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$.

from 202 °C to 209 °C over the first 3 h (2.3 °C/h). Based on this behavior, a thermal response of approximately 3.2 °C in the reactor was observed for every 1 °C increase in oil temperature, when the reactor was operating below 210 °C.

Under these conditions, the highest temperature along the catalyst bed was observed at MP 3. This likely results from the combined effect of feed gas heating and the localized intensification of the exothermic reaction at that position. As a result, by the time the gas mixture reaches MP 3, both the extent of the reaction and heat accumulation are more pronounced. Additionally, due to the counter-current flow configuration of the thermal oil—acting as a coolant—it reaches this section of the reactor at a slightly higher temperature, reducing its capacity to absorb heat efficiently. This combination likely contributes to the observed temperature peak at MP 3. Notably, as the overall reactor temperature increases over time, the MP 3 profile increasingly deviates from the other measuring points, suggesting localized heat accumulation and a region of intensified reaction. Moreover, the temperature difference between the hottest and coolest points in the reactor increases as the temperature rises. This trend indicates that the system becomes more thermally sensitive at higher operating temperatures. Such behavior emphasizes the need for precise thermal control to avoid localized overheating, which could lead to catalyst degradation or runaway conditions.

Fig. 5(b) presents the heating rate dynamics for this experiment. The oil was initially heated at a controlled rate of 0.8 °C/h, applied in pulses of 0.2 °C every 15 min. Under these conditions, the reactor exhibited HRR ranging from 2 °C/h to 3.6 °C/h. Between 3.5 – 4.5 h, the heating rate of the oil bath was halted (setpoint fixed at 201 °C) to stabilize the system. The reactor responded with good temperature stability, maintaining nearly constant temperatures along the reactor bed for approximately 1 h. Then, at 5.0 h, the oil heating protocol was intensified to two pulses of 0.5 °C every 30 min (a rate of 1.0 °C/h). This adjustment led to a HRR inside the reactor of up to 5.2 °C/h. Using these startup protocol, we were able to successfully stabilize the reaction bed at 10 bar, within the temperature range of 204–217 °C, while keeping the refrigerant temperature at 202 °C without any runaway behavior. As reported by BP and Johnson Matthey in patent application EP 4 202 018 A1 (Hamer et al., 2023), maintaining the reactor heating rate below 8 °C/h during start-up is critical to prevent thermal runaway. Our pilot-scale results experimentally validate this approach, demonstrating stable reactor operation under carefully controlled heating and pressure conditions.

At the normal operating pressure of the system of 20 bar, Fig. 6 shows the temperature and heating rate profiles of the oil system and reactor during the heating stage. Previously, the reactor was pre-heated and stabilized at 10 bar and later pressurized up to 20 bar. In this region,

Fig. 6. Effect of thermal oil heating on reactor temperature at 20 bar during reactor heating above 205 °C. (a) Temperature profile at reactor points T1 to T6. (b) Corresponding reactor thermal rate in the FTS reactor. Reaction conditions: $P = 20$ bar; $GHSV = 1250 \text{ Ncm}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$.

we show the thermal behavior of the system when heated at the initial conditions shown in Fig. 6(a), which are: 198.2 °C at the oil bath, and 202.5 – 205.6 °C inside the reactor. A key observation is that when the oil temperature increased from 198.2 °C to 199.4 °C, the temperature at MP 6 rose by 5.3 °C, indicating a reactor thermal rate of approximately 4.4 °C per 1 °C increase in the oil temperature. This is 1.2 °C higher than the thermal rate observed at 10 bar, showing that the system becomes more thermally sensitive at higher pressures. This increased sensitivity underscores the critical importance of tightly controlled heating at elevated pressures to avoid triggering runaway conditions.

Fig. 6(b) presents the HRR, while the oil was maintained at a heating rate of 0.6 °C/h, applied as pulses of 0.1 °C every 10 min. The HRR remained below 5 °C/h until approximately 1.8 h, as also reflected in the uniform heating curves shown in Fig. 6(a). Beyond 1.8 h, the reactor temperatures at MP 5 and MP 6 began to increase at rates exceeding 5 °C/h, signaling the onset of a thermal runaway. At 2.0 h, the MP 6 had a heating rate of 6.9 °C/h, and it is observed that despite decreasing the heating rate at the thermal oil to 0 °C/h at 2.2 h and -1.2 °C/h at 2.3 h, the reactor continued increasing its heating rate and entered into runaway regime, reaching temperatures of 282 °C at MP 6 (not shown in the graph). These results demonstrate again that exceeding a HRR of 15 °C/h inside the reactor, especially favoured at higher pressure, leads to runaway regime in the system.

Fig. 7 shows the CO conversion (X_{CO}) and heat duty (Q) for the experiments presented in Figs. 5 and 6. At 10 bar (Fig. 7a), X_{CO} increased from 15 % at 200 °C to 23 % at 215 °C. In comparison, at 20 bar, X_{CO} rose from 17.7 % at 205 °C to 42 % at 220 °C. The corresponding heat duty trends are shown in Fig. 7(b). At 10 bar, Q increased from 78 kW/m³ at 200 °C to 121 kW/m³ at 215 °C, whereas at 20 bar, it rose from 95 kW/m³ at 205 °C to 223 kW/m³ at 220 °C. The steeper slope observed at 20 bar (8.3 kW·m⁻³·°C⁻¹ vs. 2.7 kW·m⁻³·°C⁻¹ at 10 bar) highlights the stronger pressure dependence of heat release and the enhanced thermal response of the system under higher pressure.

In comparison with the packed-bed system reported by (Boymans et al., 2025), our approach enabled stable operation by maintaining the heating rate below the critical threshold. Under these conditions, our system reached a CO conversion of 30 % and a maximum temperature of 220 °C, in contrast to the 10 % conversion and system runaway reported in their study. Similarly, (Shen et al., 2021, 2020) reported punctual experimental results that were assumed to be obtained under stable operation; however, their work was limited to a maximum temperature of 200 °C and employed a catalyst bed configuration consisting of a 1:3 vol ratio of catalyst to ceramic balls, markedly different from that used in the present study. Taken together, these comparisons emphasize the advantages of our system in sustaining stability under more demanding operating conditions and contribute to a clearer definition of

Fig. 7. (a) CO conversion (X_{CO}) and (b) Heat duty (Q) comparison at 10 and 20 bar related to experiments shown in Figs. 5 and 6.

the operational window for low-temperature Fischer–Tropsch synthesis.

3.2. Effect of pressurization

Based on previous evidence indicating that increased pressure enhances the reactor's sensitivity to temperature variations, this section examines the effect of controlled pressurization on the system's thermal behavior. As shown in Fig. 8(a), increasing the pressure from 12 to 20 bar at a rate of 3 bar/h (0.5 bar every 10 min) led to a temperature rise at MP 3 from 205 °C to 208.8 °C—an increase of 3.8 °C over 4 h—corresponding to a heating rate of 1.0 °C/h. By comparison, oil heating at 10 bar (202–209 °C) resulted in a higher heating rate of 2.3 °C/h at MP 3 (Fig. 6a), indicating that pressurization yields a more gradual thermal response under similar temperature conditions.

Fig. 8(b) shows a linear correlation between pressure and reactor temperature, with a thermal rate of approximately 0.5 °C/bar. This is significantly lower than the 3.2 °C/°C rate observed during oil heating, confirming that pressurization at a controlled rate imposes less thermal stress on the system than external heating. The gradual temperature increases from 205 °C to 210 °C during pressurization occurred without any signs of thermal instability or runaway, indicating that a pressurization rate of 3 bar/h provides a safer and more controlled approach for reactor startup. These results contrast with the behavior observed in Fig. 6, where the system experienced runaway conditions under a heating ramp within a similar temperature range.

As expected, increasing the pressure led to a higher reactor hotspot temperature, in agreement with observations by Wang et al., 2003. This trend can be explained by the FTS kinetics described in Eq. (2), where pressure is predicted to raise the CO consumption rate (r_{CO}) by a factor of 1.23, based on the previously discussed kinetic parameters. The higher CO conversion is directly linked to an increase in heat release, as shown in Fig. 9: Q_{vol} rises from 64 to 97 kW/m³, corresponding to a slope of 4.1 kW·m⁻³·bar⁻¹ with respect to pressurization.

Overall, these insights into the internal thermal response of the catalyst bed to temperature and pressure variations enabled us to establish a protocol that combines controlled heating and pressurization, stabilizing the reaction bed above 205 °C at 20 bar. In comparison, Boymans et al. conducted a similar experiment in a packed-bed reactor with 100 g of micro-sized catalyst at 20 bar and a flow rate of 9639 Ncm³/h·g_{cat}. In their case, heating the thermal oil from 180 °C to 200 °C required 10 h, and after 13 h of continuous heating at 2 °C/h, thermal runaway occurred (Boymans et al., 2025). By contrast, in our system the same reactor temperature was achieved in less than 2 h under stable operation by reducing the oil heating rate at higher temperatures (< 2 °C/h).

Fig. 8. Effect of pressurization on maximum reactor temperature (MP 3) with thermal oil set to 199.2 °C. (a) Evolution of system pressure and corresponding MP 3 temperature profile over time. (b) Correlation of MP 3 with system pressure. Reaction conditions: GHSV = 1250 Ncm³·h⁻¹·g_{cat}⁻¹.

Fig. 9. CO conversion and Heat duty during pressurization from 12 to 20 bar.

Visconti et al, following their established startup methodology of initiating the reaction at 180 °C, required approximately 80 hours to increase the thermal oil temperature to 200 °C (resulting in approximately 201 °C within the packed-bed reactor) and 180 hours to reach 215 °C (with the highest reactor temperature recorded at 218 °C) (Visconti et al., 2024). Their system operated at a GHSV of 4000 cm³/h·g_{cat} and 25 bar. By comparison, we reached a reactor temperature of 205 °C with the thermal oil at 198.6 °C, in around only 2 h. This highlights the importance of optimizing startup conditions not only to prevent runaway scenarios, but also to reduce reaction time and gas consumption—key factors under pilot plant operation.

3.3. Effect of GHSV

To assess whether the criterion of maintaining the HRR below 15 °C/h remains valid under different GHSV conditions, additional experiments were conducted, as shown in Fig. 10. Panels (a, c, e) display the reactor temperature profiles during heating at 20 bar for various gas hourly space velocities (GHSVs), while panels (b, d, f) show the corresponding heating rate responses (HRRs) at seven measuring points (MPs 2–8) along the catalyst bed, as indicated in panel (g). The experiments were carried out sequentially, with the system cooled before each change in GHSV to prevent runaway. Under these conditions, the reactor temperatures were consistently lower than the oil temperature, in contrast to the behavior observed in the previous experiments (Figs. 3–7). This difference can be attributed to the non-adiabatic nature

Fig. 10. Effect of thermal oil heating on reactor temperature and heating rate response (HRR) at 20 bar for different gas hourly space velocities (GHSV): (a, b) $500 \text{ Ncm}^3\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$, (c, d) $1000 \text{ Ncm}^3\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$, and (e, f) $2000 \text{ Ncm}^3\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$ (g) Catalyst bed disposition and measuring points (MP). Reaction conditions: $P = 20 \text{ bar}$; Non-adiabatic system.

of the system, where part of the released heat dissipated to the surroundings. Notably, in all cases the HRR remained below the critical threshold of $15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/h}$; indeed, in most cases, it remained below $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/h}$.

3.4. Reactor performance

By following an appropriate startup protocol—ensuring a reactor thermal rate below $8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/h}$ during temperature and pressure increase in the system—a stable startup of the pilot plant was attained. Fig. 11 presents the experimentally measured temperature distribution in the tubular fixed-bed reactor at 20 bar, recorded at different operating times at stable conditions (1, 12, and 24 h), where z represents the distance

from the reactor inlet. Since the FTS process is highly exothermic, it generates a characteristic temperature profile along the reactor bed.

The temperature profiles show the lowest temperature at MP 1 ($z = 11 \text{ cm}$), a deviation attributed to the low temperature of the feed gases entering the reactor ($< 180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). As the gases progress through the reactor, the temperature rises, reaching a peak at MP 3 ($z = 17 \text{ cm}$). This increase is likely due to an increase of reaction conversion (X_{CO}), and the thermal equilibrium reached between the heat released from the reaction advancing downstream, and the counter-current recirculating oil bath (refrigerant). Although the formation of hot spots is typical in these kinds of chemical reactors, (Dai et al., 2014; Shen et al., 2021a) we observed a maximum temperature difference of $\sim 6.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ along the

Fig. 11. Temperature profiles along the reactor (solid lines) at time-on-stream of 1, 12 and 24 h and oil temperature (red dashed line). Reaction conditions: $P = 20$ bar; $GHSV = 1250 \text{ Ncm}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$.

reaction bed in the section between MP 2 and MP 6. During the 24 h of reaction, a slight temperature decrease was observed in MP 3, which is associated with the typical decline in conversion over time during FTS. Note that at MP 5 ($z = 23$ cm), an aluminum alloy (AlSi10Mg) temperature probe holder was installed as part of the reactor setup. This component could enhance local heat diffusion, which may explain the observed decrease in MP 5, followed by a slight increase in temperature in MP 6.

Fig. 12 presents the reaction products and their selectivity. In Fig. 12 (a), the product distribution in terms of molar selectivity is shown, averaged over 25 h of operation. During this period, the system operated at 20 bar and an average temperature of 210 °C (see Fig. 8), achieving a mean CO conversion of 20 %. The obtained selectivity presents a typical FTS hydrocarbon distribution, with a CH_4 selectivity lower than 10 %, and 25 % of products in the diesel range ($\text{C}_{12} - \text{C}_{18}$), and 28 % of products in the wax fraction (C_{19+}), indicating effective chain growth under the selected conditions. The selectivity products profile follows the Anderson-Schulz-Flory (ASF) distribution, with a chain growth probability (α) of 0.89. This value reflects a strong tendency toward the formation of long-chain hydrocarbons, consistent with cobalt-based catalysts operating at 20 bar.

Moreover, Fig. 12 (b) presents the weight fraction distribution of

Fig. 12. (a) Product distribution in molar selectivity (b) Characterization of liquid and wax in weight fraction of Low Temperature FTS reaction. Reaction conditions: $P = 20$ bar, $GHSV = 1250 \text{ Ncm}^3 / \text{h} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{cat}}$.

hydrocarbons collected in the cold and hot traps (corresponding to the liquid and wax phases, respectively), as analyzed by GC/MSD. The liquid fraction consists primarily of hydrocarbons ranging from C_7 to C_{20} , with the highest concentration between C_9 and C_{13} , while the wax fraction contains heavier hydrocarbons starting from C_{11} , with a predominance of species in the $\text{C}_{18} - \text{C}_{24}$ range. These results show that by appropriately controlling the startup conditions, we were able to sustain FTS reaction conditions at 20 bar, in a pilot-plant, using a supported cobalt micro-size catalyst, and successfully produced synthetic liquid hydrocarbons and waxes, which play a crucial role in the development of cleaner fuels and renewable chemicals.

4. Conclusions

This work analyzed the effect of controlled thermal and pressure variations during the startup of a FTS pilot plant loaded with micro-sized cobalt catalysts. The reactor showed high sensitivity to changes in thermal oil heating, underscoring the need for precise control of both temperature and pressure to ensure safe and stable operation.

Maintaining a heating rate below 15 °C/h was identified as a key factor in preventing excessive temperature increases and avoiding thermal runaway. The system's response varied with catalyst reactivity and operating conditions that enhance conversion, such as elevated temperatures and pressures. However, a controlled ramp-up of temperature at the catalyst bed proved effective in mitigating thermal instability. Stable operation was achieved by limiting the oil heating rate to below 0.8 °C/h, which corresponds to internal reactor rates below 15 °C. Additionally, pressure was safely increased at a controlled rate of 3 bar/h within the 12 – 20 bar range.

Importantly, results indicate that, within specific temperature intervals, implementing a pressure ramp instead of a thermal ramp provides a safer and more effective strategy to control the reactor's thermal response. Therefore, the combination of temperature and pressure ramping emerges as a key operational strategy for safe startup.

These findings demonstrate that the thermal stabilization of a pilot-scale FTS system is feasible through the implementation of a carefully designed startup protocol. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of the reactor's temperature response are essential for maintaining operational stability and minimizing safety risks during pressurized operation of exothermic catalytic systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jordi Guilera Sala: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis,

Conceptualization. **Martí Biset-Peiró**: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Andrés A. García Blanco**: Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Karen Quintana**: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work is part of the SUPORT (PLEC2022-009250) and VALOTAIL (PID2023-151777OB-I00) projects, funded by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER, UE, part of the research program funded by funds from the Next Generation Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.psep.2025.107849](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2025.107849).

References

- Arcuri, K.B., Rouge, B., 1986. Process for the start-up of Fischer-Tropsch reaction [US Patent US4626552A].
- Bezemer, G.L., Mester, C.M.A.M., Den Breejen, J.P., 2025. A method for start-up and operation of a Fischer-Tropsch reactor. EP 3 119 856 B1.
- Boymans, E., Ganjkanlou, Y., Denneman, M., Sutens, B., Lefevre, J., Grootjes, S., 2025. Structured internals for the intensified Fischer-Tropsch synthesis in fixed-bed reactors. *React. Chem. Eng.* 10, 686–693. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4RE00550C>.
- Chikati, R., Mpandanyama, T.A., Nkazi, D., Khangale, P., Gorimbo, J., 2024. Optimization and evaluation of the distribution of Fischer-tropsch products over a cobalt-based catalyst utilising design expert software. *Heliyon* 10, e23145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23145>.
- Dai, X.P., Liu, P.Z., Shi, Y., Xu, J., Wei, W.S., 2014. Fischer-Tropsch synthesis in a bench-scale two-stage multitubular fixed-bed reactor: simulation and enhancement in conversion and diesel selectivity. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 105, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2013.09.057>.
- Ermolaev, V.S., Gryaznov, K.O., Mitberg, E.B., Mordkovich, V.Z., Tretyakov, V.F., 2015. Laboratory and pilot plant fixed-bed reactors for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis: mathematical modeling and experimental investigation. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 138, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2015.07.036>.
- Fernandes, F.A.N., 2006. Optimization of Fischer-Tropsch synthesis using neural networks. *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 29, 449–453. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.200500310>.
- Fratolocchi, L., Groppi, G., Visconti, C.G., Lietti, L., Tronconi, E., 2020. Adoption of 3D printed highly conductive periodic open cellular structures as an effective solution to enhance the heat transfer performances of compact Fischer-Tropsch fixed-bed reactors. *Chem. Eng. J.* 386, 123988. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.123988>.
- Gholami, Z., Tisler, Z., Šimek, J., 2023. Effect of multilayered catalytic bed on temperature profiles and catalytic performance for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis over Co/Al₂O₃ catalyst in a multitubular fixed-bed reactor. *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* 197, 274–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2023.07.038>.
- Ghouri, M.M., Afzal, S., Hussain, R., Blank, J., Bukur, D.B., Elbashir, N.O., 2016. Multi-scale modeling of fixed-bed Fischer Tropsch reactor. *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 91, 38–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2016.03.035>.
- Guilera, J., del Valle, J., Alarcón, A., Díaz, J.A., Andreu, T., 2019. Metal-oxide promoted Ni/Al₂O₃ as CO₂ methanation micro-size catalysts. *J. CO₂ Util.* 30, 11–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2019.01.003>.
- Hamer, C.K., British Petroleum (BP), Johnson Matthey, 2023. Fischer Tropsch Synthesis start-up.
- IREC, 2023. The SUPORT project will revalorize CO₂ as a fuel for maritime transport [WWW Document]. URL (Accessed 9.2.24)(<https://www.irec.cat/press-society/news/the-support-project-will-revalorize-co2-as-a-fuel-for-maritime-transport/>).
- Kaskes, B., Vervloet, D., Kapteijn, F., van Ommen, J.R., 2016. Numerical optimization of a structured tubular reactor for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. *Chem. Eng. J.* 283, 1465–1483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2015.08.078>.
- Kummer, A., Varga, T., 2021. What do we know already about reactor runaway? – A review. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 147, 460–476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2020.09.059>.
- Lwazzani, M.A., García Blanco, A.A., Biset-Peiró, M., Martín Morales, E., Guilera, J., 2024. Unveiling the influence of activation protocols on cobalt catalysts for sustainable fuel synthesis. *Catalysts* 14, 920. <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal14120920>.
- Okano, H., Nagao, A., Matsubara, K., Ishikawa, N., Takagi, S., Kitagawa, S., Takano, T., 2019. Assessment of leak before break of a newly developed type ii pressure vessel with high-pressure hydrogen gas. Codes and Standards 1 American Society of Mechanical Engineers, doi: [doi:10.1115/PVP2019-93447](https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2019-93447).
- Pandey, U., Putta, K.R., Rout, K.R., Blekkan, E.A., Rytter, E., Hillestad, M., 2022. Staging and path optimization of Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* 187, 276–289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2022.08.033>.
- Panzeri, M., Visconti, C.G., Groppi, G., Tronconi, E., 2025. Process intensification of the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis using conductive packed POCS with skin: the role of the POCS design parameters. *Chem. Eng. J.* 521, 166359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.166359>.
- Quintana, K., García Blanco, A.A., Bernadet, L., Ruiz, D., Torrell, M., Guilera, J., 2024. Resource availability for e-MGO adoption in maritime transport: a case study in the port of barcelona. *Energy Convers. Manag.* X 24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2024.100800>.
- Saada, R., Patel, D., Saha, B., 2015. Causes and consequences of thermal runaway incidents—Will they ever be avoided? *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 97, 109–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2015.02.005>.
- Shen, J., Ho, W.H., Liu, X., Hildebrandt, D., 2021. Tubular reactor internals for suppressing hot spot formation applied to the Fischer-Tropsch reaction. *Chem. Eng. Process. Process. Intensif.* 161, 108309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2021.108309>.
- Shen, J., Li, Y., Ho, W.H., Liu, X., Hildebrandt, D., 2020. Experimental and simulation study of the temperature distribution in a bench-scale fixed bed Fischer-Tropsch reactor. *AIChE J.* 67. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aic.17145> e17145.
- Tian, Y., Zou, Q., Jin, Z., Lin, Z., 2022. Data-driven diagnosis of the high-pressure hydrogen leakage in fuel cell vehicles based on relevance vector machine. *Int. J. Hydrog. Energy* 47, 12281–12292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.08.148>.
- Visconti, C.G., Panzeri, M., Groppi, G., Tronconi, E., 2024. Heat transfer intensification in compact tubular reactors with cellular internals: a pilot-scale assessment of highly conductive packed-POCS with skin applied to the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. *Chem. Eng. J.* 481, 148469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.148469>.
- Zhang, H., Bai, M., Wang, X., Gai, J., Shu, C.-M., Roy, N., Liu, Y., 2021. Thermal runaway incidents—a serious cause of concern: an analysis of runaway incidents in China. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* 155, 277–286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2021.09.027>.
- Zhang, Q., Cheng, K., Kang, J., Deng, W., Wang, Y., 2014. Fischer-Tropsch catalysts for the production of hydrocarbon fuels with high selectivity. *ChemSusChem* 7, 1251–1264. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.201300797>.